

PLANNING FOR BORDER SETTLEMENT AREAS PRIORITY LOCATION II JAGOI BABANG, BENGKAYANG REGENCY, WEST KALIMANTAN 2018

Rino Wicaksono *

Architecture Program, Institut Teknologi Indonesia, Kota Tangerang Selatan, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: rinowicaksono656@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11616564](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11616564)

Abstract

Indonesia is a country rich in diverse resources, which should be able to improve the welfare of its people. However, there are still isolated areas, such as border areas with minimal infrastructure, poor residential environmental quality, and low community welfare, and even access to border areas is quite challenging to reach. All Indonesian citizens have the right to a decent living through the provision of housing and residential areas, which are citizens' basic needs. Law no. 1 of 2011 concerning Housing and Settlement Areas states that the state is responsible for protecting the entire Indonesian nation by implementing housing and residential areas so that people can live and live in decent and affordable homes in healthy, safe, harmonious, and sustainable housing throughout the region. Indonesia. In this case, the Central Government has the authority and obligation to develop state border areas in accordance with the mandate of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning the Regional Government. This research aims to provide an integrated, directed, and sustainable development plan document for border settlement areas referring to spatial planning documents in accordance with the area's character, potential, and carrying capacity by considering applicable technical rules and standards. The method used is a qualitative survey type, and the research location is in the Jagoi Babang border settlement area, Bengkayang Regency, West Kalimantan Province. Data analysis using the DED Master Plan. The research results are the particular regional development strategies for West Kalimantan Province for 2013-2018, which relate to infrastructure problems in border areas: First, Regional Development Policy Strategy, second, Basic Infrastructure Development Policy Strategy, third, Border Area Development Policy Strategy.

Keywords: Planning, Border Settlement Area Priority Location II Jagoi Babang, Bengkayang Regency, West Kalimantan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing border areas is intended to strengthen state sovereignty, improve community welfare, and make border areas the front porch of a competitive country (Situmorang & Ayustia, 2019). This is in line with the direction of the President's Nawacita, namely, to develop Indonesia from the periphery by strengthening regions and villages within the framework of a unitary state. Development of border areas in the 2015-2019 RPJMN is focused on 10 National Strategic Activity Centers (PKSN) and 187 Priority Location Districts (Lokpri) in 41 Regencies/Cities and 13 Provinces (Nurussalam & Supriyono, 2023). Developing border residential areas is also intended to realize the RPJMN target: developing residential areas in 3,099 particular areas (Nday et al., 2023).

Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing through the Sub-Directorate of Special Settlement Areas, Directorate of Residential Area Development, Directorate General. Cipta Karya also carries out the task of organizing the development of border residential areas where PUPR Ministerial Decree No. 15/PRT/M/2015 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing states the duties and functions of the Sub-Directorate of Special Settlement Areas to carry out facilitation and technical assistance for the implementation of notable

settlements covering border areas, outermost small islands, disaster-prone areas, post-disaster, and certain areas determined by statutory regulations (Amini et al., 2018).

To support the implementation of the development of particular residential areas in border areas, a directed, integrated, and implementable plan is needed (Suni et al., 2023). Therefore, the Sub-Directorate of Special Settlement Areas, Directorate of Settlement Area Development, in the 2018 fiscal year, prepared a Border Settlement Area Plan for Priority Location II: Jagoi Babang, Bengkayang Regency, West Kalimantan Province. Hopefully, this planning can guide the development of border areas to grow into livable, competitive, and sustainable regions (Rusmiyati et al., 2022).

Apart from that, this research aims to realize good quality border settlements in Jagoi Babang, Bengkayang Regency, West Kalimantan Province through developing settlement infrastructure within a predetermined time frame (Moniaga, 2018). Then, to provide an integrated, directed, and sustainable border settlement area development plan document referring to spatial planning documents following the character (Maisondra & Timur, 2023), the potential and carrying capacity of the area by considering applicable technical rules and standards (Suryani et al., 2015).

2. METHODS

The research method used is field observation, and qualitative survey activities carried out to identify existing and potential conditions (Abduh et al., 2023), problems, obstacles, and challenges (SWOT) of residential areas, and residential infrastructure at work locations (Pahleviannur et al., 2022). Then, coordinate with relevant stakeholders at the work location to identify strategic issues, regional development direction plans, potential problems, obstacles and challenges (SWOT), and residential infrastructure development plans (Maidiana, 2021).

Qualitative methods emphasize observing phenomena and researching the substance of the meaning of these phenomena. Basri (2014) concluded that qualitative research focuses on the process and meaning of the results. Qualitative research focuses on efforts to understand an event, behavior, or phenomenon (Mohamed, Abdul Majid & Ahmad, 2010).

The research objects include inventorying policies/regulations (Basyah & A Razak, 2020), compiling the results of policy/regulation studies, carrying out identification of conditions and strategic issues, carrying out coordination with stakeholders to obtain input on concepts and plans for development and structuring in the scope of work areas, carrying out surveys field for measurement and confirmation of field data in developed/organized areas; Compiling the results of analysis of infrastructure and facility needs, compiling concepts and handling strategies, compiling program matrices, activities and indications of costs for implementing physical and non-physical activities; Arranged master plan development, Preparation of detailed planning drawings, including architectural, structural drawings, network plans and other detailed drawings as directed masterplan which has been prepared; Preparation of Work Plan documents and Requirements and Cost Budget Plans; Compilation of work implementation reports. Research location in the Jagoi Babang border settlement area, Bengkayang Regency, West Kalimantan Province (Fiantika et al., 2022).

Data analysis uses the Master Plan and DED (Nday et al., 2023). Analysis activities carried out include: (policy and regulatory analysis, institutional analysis, population analysis, economic analysis, socio-cultural analysis, land use pattern analysis, analysis of community activities, spatial analysis, architectural analysis, achievement/accessibility analysis;

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 2013-2018 West Kalimantan Development Vision formulated in the 2013-2018 West Kalimantan Regional Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMD) is: "to create a faithful, healthy, intelligent, safe, cultured and prosperous West Kalimantan community" to achieve this vision. has been determined, a mission is needed, especially those related to infrastructure problems in border areas, as in the following table.

Table 1: Goals and Targets of the West Kalimantan Province RPJMD Regarding Infrastructure To Optimize the Economic Potential of Border Areas

Objective	Target
Mission 9: Carry out increased development of basic infrastructure to facilitate population mobility and the flow of goods, as well as accelerate development in interior, border, coastal, and island areas as a source of economic potential	
1. Improving the quality and quantity of infrastructure to optimize the economic potential of inland, border, coastal and island areas	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An integrated road infrastructure network and bridges between modes are needed to support the movement of people, goods, and services. 2. Availability of water resources infrastructure, swamp areas, and area proper irrigation to support efforts for water security, controlling the destructive power of water and food security. 3. Housing and settlement facilities and infrastructure are available, including the sanitation and clean water. 4. Increasing the fulfillment of the need for uninhabitable housing as well as meeting the need for public facilities infrastructure in residential areas 5. Availability of adequate and integrated land, sea, and air transportation infrastructure to support the movement of people, goods, and services 6. Communication and information technology facilities, infrastructure, and services are available evenly throughout the West Kalimantan region. 7. Increase the supply of clean water in the area. Water shortages and insufficient electricity supply in the region of West Kalimantan with energy development based on new and renewable energy.

Source: West Kalimantan Province RPJMD 2013 - 2018

The special regional development strategy for West Kalimantan Province for 2013-2018 relating to infrastructure problems in border areas is as follows:

1. Regional Development Policy Strategy

The regional development policy strategy will be divided into 3 (three) development areas, namely inland areas, border areas (between provinces and between countries), and coastal and island areas (Entikong, n.d.)

2. Basic Infrastructure Development Policy Strategy

The basic infrastructure development policy strategy is carried out with a focus on (a) production center areas to facilitate community accessibility to market access, (b) Building infrastructure that focuses on supporting the investment system and community accessibility to regional development programs, (c) Building tourism

infrastructure in destination areas and superior tourist attractions in the Regency/City (Boymau et al., 2023).

3. Border Area Development Policy Strategy

The border region development policy strategy is carried out through (a) A security approach by strengthening order and security in the border region (b) A welfare approach, with a focus on improving the standard of living and welfare of the community as well as increasing the capacity to manage regional potential; (c) An environmental approach while maintaining a balance between economic interests and ecological interests (Wangke, 2018)

The policies and strategies for the spatial structure of the West Kalimantan region aim to realize equitable regional growth by maintaining environmental balance and the availability of natural resources. Strengthening the role of urban areas in West Kalimantan according to the functions that have been determined, namely the National Activity Center (PKN), National Activity Center – Provincial system (PKNp), Regional Activity Center (PKW), Regional Activity Center – Provincial system (PKWp), and Activity Center Local (PKL). Strategy to strengthen the role of urban areas in West Kalimantan according to the established functions, namely PKN, PKNp, PKW, PKWp, and PKL. National strategic areas are areas whose spatial planning is prioritized because they have a significant influence nationally on state sovereignty, state defense and security, economy, society, culture and/or environment, including areas designated as world heritage (Kameo & Huruta, 2019). Provincial strategic areas are areas whose spatial planning is prioritized because they have a significant influence within the province on the economy, society, culture and/or environment (Purnamasari et al., 2016).

Based on the spatial structure directions of Bengkayang Regency, a Type B Terminal in Jagoi Babang District is planned to be built. Meanwhile, according to the direction of the Bengkayang Regency spatial pattern plan, Jagoi Babang District functions as an Other Use Area (APL), Limited Production Forest (HPT) area, and Convertible Production Forest (HPK) area. Limited Production Forest Designation Areas are determined using the criteria of slope, soil type, and rain intensity with a total score of 125 (one hundred and twenty-five) to 174 (one hundred and seventy-four) (Arnowo, 2018). The Limited Production Forest (HPT) area in Bengkayang Regency is located in Sungai Betung, Bengkayang, Lumar, Selebar, Jagoi Babang, and Siding Districts with approximately 46,724 Ha. Bengkayang Regency tourism destination development strategies include (Muta'Ali et al., 2018):

- 1) Developing cultural tourism that glorifies nature and displays creativity that has a local/unique identity and is competitive
- 2) The development of tourist attractions is focused on tourist attractions that support the sustainable development of superior tourist areas.
- 3) Development of man-made tourism that supports the tourism development theme of Bengkayang Regency by exploiting the potential of superior tourist attractions;
- 4) Developing integrated tourism with other international-standard tourist destinations adjacent to Bengkayang Regency, such as Singkawang and Sambas.

- 5) Exploring, preserving, and developing the cultural heritage of Bengkayang Regency as a Cultural Tourism Attraction;
- 6) Cultural Tourism Attractions in the form of Traditional Rituals as Special Attractions need to be protected and limited from exploitation by tourists;
- 7) Traditional markets need to be organized and improve the quality of their services. Thus, that they have the potential to become tourist attractions for human-made products;
- 8) The Art Market is a human-made tourist attraction that is most popular with foreign tourists and domestic tourists;
- 9) Raising the potential of the District's Tourism Attraction.
- 10) Increasing accessibility to the city's leading tourist areas through improving and maintaining transportation facilities and infrastructure, both land and sea as well as improving the quality of transportation services and infrastructure;
- 11) Increasing ease of accessibility between BWPPs in Bengkayang Regency, especially supporting accessibility between the mother of Bengkayang Regency and the provincial capital, the Regional Activity Center (PKW), and the Environmental Activity Center (PKL) with the Regency's Leading Tourism Area (KWUK);
- 12) Increased accessibility between Featured Tourist Attractions (DTWU) in each District's Featured Tourism Area; Development of Transportation Network Systems, such as primary arterial roads, primary collector roads, primary local roads, and secondary system roads.
- 13) Development of Transportation Network Systems includes primary arterial roads, collector roads, primary local roads, and secondary system roads.
- 14) Increasing the provision and services of clean water, electricity, and telecommunications infrastructure to support tourism development, especially in the Regency's Leading Tourism Areas.
- 15) Maintaining the cleanliness of mangrove forests in Bengkayang Regency and increasing tourist attractions in mangrove forest areas, which can increase the number of visits by foreign and domestic tourists;
- 16) Increase the availability of infrastructure and public facilities in tourism areas so that tourist activities can be carried out comfortably and safely.
- 17) The Bengkayang Regency Government needs to plan pedestrian and revitalization actions for street furniture to create comfort and safety for pedestrians and tourists with disabilities, special attention needs to be given; And
- 18) Realizing Sapta Pesona in Bengkayang Regency.

Bengkayang Regency's tourism marketing development strategy includes First, Tourist Market Development, Tourism Image Development, Tourism Marketing Partnership Development, and Tourism Promotion Development. Apart from that, there are several tourism marketing development strategies for Bengkayang Regency, including First, Developing the foreign tourist market (tourists) by attracting foreign tourists from the nearest market source areas. Second, develop a market for foreign tourists and tourists interested in tourism with natural and cultural nuances. Third

Development of the domestic tourist market (wisnus) by optimally utilizing the potential of tourist attractions in Bengkayang Regency. Fourth, an effective and integrated marketing and promotion system must be developed (Ruhmana et al., 2019). Artificial tourist attractions also need to be developed.

Then, there are several Bengkayang Regency Tourism Industry Development Strategies, First, Increased coordination and consolidation between government institutions at sub-district and district levels, between government institutions, the private sector, and the community in tourism development in Bengkayang Regency; Second, Developing partnerships/cooperation with neighboring countries, world organizations, and domestic experts in developing the tourism industry in Bengkayang Regency; Third Development of the tourism industry, especially in response to environmental and cultural preservation programs as well as improving human welfare.

Furthermore, the Bengkayang Regency Tourism Institutional Development Strategy includes, First, Increased coordination and consolidation between government institutions at sub-district and district levels, between government institutions, the private sector, and the community in developing tourism in Bengkayang Regency; Second, Developing partnerships/cooperation with neighboring countries, world organizations and domestic experts in creating natural, cultural and mixed tourism in Bengkayang Regency; Third Development of tourism education institutions as producers of competent/quality tourism human resources following market demands.

From the planning of the distribution on the site, it can be roughly divided into three zones, namely, the sacred zone, an area used for cultural ritual processions of the Dayak Bidayuh tribe. A transitional zone, which is planned as an area with an allocation as a place where baluk buildings from the Dayak Bidayuh sub-tribe others are built, and a profane zone where facilities such as open spaces/gardens, souvenir shops, local culinary stands, workshop areas, and performance venues in the form of amphitheatres/open stages, as well as cultural village management rooms, are planned.

Figure 1: Jagoi Babang Cultural Village Zoning Concept

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

The zoning/regional concept results can determine the placement or regionalization of the mass of buildings and facilities to be designed in the cultural village area.

Figure 2: Buildings and Facilities in Each Zone

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

Planning concept entrance featuring a gate that adapts one of the traditional forms of architecture of the Dayak Bidayuh Tribe as an implementation or embodiment of local traditional architectural culture. The gate concept also reflects an area of cultural tourism facilities by featuring local ethnic nuances that facilitate visitors' introduction to the development area of the Jagoi Babang Cultural Village.

Figure 3: Concept of Entrance to Jagoi Babang Cultural Village

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

Placement entrance considering the ease of access from the existing road as the primary access to cultural villages' site (site) development.

Figure 4: Position Entrance

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

3.1 Outdoor Space Concept

Elements softscape in the form of vegetation selected from types of vegetation that are easy and cheap to maintain, are compatible with the surrounding environment, and can show the natural characteristics of the local area, cultivating shrubs and trees capable of producing oxygen and absorbing carbon emissions. For trees as well as for shade. Selection of pavement materials (hardscape) which include paving stone/paving block. This is one way to minimize standing water on the site because rainwater or water on the land's surface can be absorbed directly into the soil. The landscape concept has a natural appearance and a selection of natural materials representing the natural image of the Jagoi Babang Cultural Village. The landscape furniture concept is designed as a place to rest and interact with visitors. Apart from adding aesthetic elements and positive visual effects to the site design, this outdoor space design concept also maintains the site's sustainability, condition, and natural impression.

Figure 5: Outdoor Space Concept

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

3.2 Building View Concept

The concept of designing the appearance of the building requires maintaining the original form of the traditional buildings of the Bidayuh Dayak Tribe. Thus, that the objectives/context of the development planning can be achieved. Buildings designed as supporting facilities for tourism activities in cultural villages are also designed based on adapting the physical form of local traditional architecture, in this case the Bidayuh Dayak Tribe.

Figure 6: Building Appearance Concept

Source: Master Plan Jagoi Cultural Village in 2015

3.3 Building Structure Concept

The main concern in the concept of building structures with structural materials from natural materials and traditional construction systems is the knowledge of local workers in their application, starting from the substructure system (foundation), upper structure (Sloof, columns, and beams), and supper structures (large buildings) as well as connection systems between parts.

Figure 7: Building Structure

Source: Jagoi Cultural Village Master Plan Year 2015

4. CONCLUSION

The special regional development strategy for West Kalimantan Province for 2013-2018 relating to infrastructure problems in border areas is as follows: First, Regional Development Policy Strategy. Second is the Basic Infrastructure Development Policy Strategy, and third is the Border Area Development Policy Strategy. The Bengkayang Regency tourism marketing development strategy includes, firstly, developing the tourist market, secondly, developing the tourism image, thirdly developing tourism marketing partnerships, and fourthly, developing tourism promotions. Several strategies exist for developing tourism institutions in the Bengkayang Regency. First, increasing coordination and consolidation between government institutions at sub-district and district levels, between government institutions, the private sector, and the community in tourism development in Bengkayang Regency; second, developing partnerships/cooperation with neighboring countries, world organizations, and experts; Third, development of tourism destinations that respond to environmental and cultural preservation programs as well as improving human welfare through the development of tourist attractions, amenities, accessibility, tourism, and communities. Then there are several strategies for developing the Bengkayang Regency tourism industry, namely developing community entrepreneurship in various business fields that support the world of tourism.

References

- 1) Abduh, M., Alawiyah, T., Apriansyah, G., Sirodj, R. A., & Afgani, M. W. (2023). Survey Design: Cross Sectional dalam Penelitian Kualitatif. *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains Dan Komputer*, 3(01), 31–39.
- 2) Amini, M., Yuristiadhi, G., & Dukarno, P. D. (2018). *Kami di Antara Mereka: Pengalaman Mahasiswa KKN PPM UGM 2013*. UGM PRESS.
- 3) Arnowo, H. (2018). Penataan Penguasaan Tanah Di Kawasan Perbatasan Negara. *Jurnal Transformasi Administrasi*, 8(2), 130–146.
- 4) Basyah, N. A., & A Razak, Z. (2020). Metode kualitatif dalam riset bisnis: satu tinjauan. *Jurnal Economica Didactica*, 2(01), 15–24.
- 5) Boymau, M. H., Totnay, N. S., & Arman, Y. (2023). Implementasi Perpres Nomor 118 Tahun 2022 Tentang Rencana Induk Pengelolaan Batas Wilayah Negara dan Kawasan Perbatasan Tahun 2020-2024 Terhadap Pulau Sebatik. *Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin*, 1(7).
- 6) Entikong, F. K. S. K. I. (n.d.). *Optimalisasi Pos Lintas Batas Tradisional Dalam Pelaksanaan*.
- 7) Fiantika, F., Wasil, M., Jumiyati, S. R. I., Honesti, L., Wahyuni, S. R. I., Mouw, E., Mashudi, I., Hasanah, N. U. R., Maharani, A., & Ambarwati, K. (2022). Metodologi penelitian kualitatif. *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif. In Rake Sarasin (Issue March)*. Surabaya: PT. Pustaka Pelajar. <https://scholar.google.com/citations>.
- 8) Kameo, D. D., & Huruta, A. D. (2019). *Potret Kemiskinan di Desa Jagoi Kecamatan Jagoi Babang Kabupaten Bengkayang Propinsi Kalimantan Barat*. Program Studi Ilmu Ekonomi FEB-UKSW.
- 9) Maidiana, M. (2021). Penelitian survey. *ALACRITY: Journal of Education*, 20–29.
- 10) Maisondra, M., & Timur, F. A. C. (2023). Pembangunan Kawasan Pos Lintas Batas Negara (Plbn) Dan Dampaknya Terhadap Kebijakan Keamanan Nasional. *Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan Suara Khatulistiwa (JIPSK)*, 8(2), 210–225.
- 11) Moniaga, S. (2018). *Masyarakat adat, hukum dan hak asasi manusia di Indonesia*.
- 12) Muta'Ali, L., Marwast, D., & Christanto, J. (2018). *Pengelolaan wilayah perbatasan NKRI*. Ugm Press.

- 13) Nday, R. U., Kapilawi, Y. W. D., Maromon, R. Y. Y., Neonufa, S. N. I., Fanggidae, L. W., Bahantwelu, M., & Dahoklory, L. O. (2023). Bantuan Teknis Penyusunan Masterplan dan DED Kawasan Wisata Pantai Panmuti di Desa Noelbaki Kab Kupang NTT. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat Undana*, 17(2), 41–51.
- 14) Nurussalam, W., & Supriyono, E. (2023). Studi Kelayakan Lokasi Budidaya serta Pembuatan Masterplan di Kampung Perikanan Desa Patra Tani, Muara Enim, Sumatera Selatan. *Jurnal Akuakultur Sungai Dan Danau*, 8(1), 79–89.
- 15) Pahleviannur, M. R., De Grave, A., Saputra, D. N., Mardianto, D., Hafrida, L., Bano, V. O., Susanto, E. E., Mahardhani, A. J., Alam, M. D. S., & Lisyia, M. (2022). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Pradina Pustaka.
- 16) Purnamasari, W., Kara, M. H., AR, M. S., & Amiruddin, K. (2016). Perkembangan Pembangunan Ekonomi Kawasan Perbatasan Negara Indonesia Malaysia Di Sambas. *Jurnal Diskursus Islam*, 4(2), 217–247.
- 17) Ruhmana, I., Budiyono, D., & Nuraini, N. (2019). Analisis Potensi Kesesuaian Lahan Welcome Area Di Perbatasan Lokpri Indonesia-Malaysia, Desa Jagoi Kabupaten Bengkayang. *Fakultas Pertanian*, 7(3).
- 18) Rusmiyati, R., Hendiyani, M. F., Nooraini, A., & Alma'arif, A. (2022). *Manajemen Perbatasan*. Cendekia Press.
- 19) Situmorang, D. M., & Ayustia, R. (2019). Model Pembangunan Daerah 3T: Studi Kasus Daerah Perbatasan Kabupaten Bengkayang. *Mbia*, 18(1), 49–64.
- 20) Suni, B., Fahriansah, O., IP, S., & Sihaloho, N. T. P. (2023). *Politik Lokal Dalam Kinerja Organisasi Terhadap Efektivitas Pembangunan Partisipasif Pemerintah Daerah Pada Musrenbang*. Scopindo Media Pustaka.
- 21) Suryani, F., Trikariastoto, S., & Hadari, I. R. (2015). *Hibah Ristekdikti: Model Pembiayaan Infrastruktur Kawasan Perbatasan Indonesia–Malaysa Berdasarkan Prinsip Public Private Partnerships (Studi Kasus: Kabupaten Sambas–Sanggau, Kalimantan Barat)*.
- 22) Wangke, H. (2018). *Kerja sama Indonesia-Malaysia dalam pengelolaan perbatasan di Kalimantan*. Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.